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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AASHVI K Pbearing USN6SU20RT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABINA K Sbearing USN6SU20RT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA PRASAD bearing USN6SU20RT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANCY K Mbearing USN6SU20RT004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUVEETH bearing USN6SU20RT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWATHI Kbearing USN6SU20RT006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA HUDA Vbearing USN6SU20RT007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA NIMNA Nbearing USN6SU20RT008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIDA Kbearing USN6SU20RT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAUTHAM SANKER C Mbearing USN6SU20RT010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JAMSHITH IBRHIMbearing USN6SU20RT011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUSTIN THOMAS bearing USN6SU20RT012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIYANA UBAIDULLA bearing USN6SU20RT013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED SHIBILY bearing USN6SU20RT014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ASIF bearing USN6SU20RT015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED HAMZATH ADIL Kbearing USN6SU20RT016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SAFWAN bearing USN6SU20RT017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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**This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ABDUL SALAM T Kbearing
USN6SU20RT018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical
sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory
therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAJU MOIDEEN bearing USN6SU20RT021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHUMAIL HAMAD C P V bearing USN6SU20RT022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEGANGA C V bearing USN6SU20RT023 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms STELLA MARY bearing USN6SU20RT024 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms UNNIMAYA P Jbearing USN6SU20RT025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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